

Studies in Pyrimidobenzothiazines and Thiazinoquinazolines

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Some pyrimidobenzothiazines and their isomeric thiazinoquinazolines with amino group in position 6 have been synthesised. The former have been obtained by the condensation of (2-amino-4,5-methylenedioxybenzylidene)-amines with β -isothioyanoketones, whereas the latter have been obtained by the condensation of (2-amino-4,5-methylenedioxybenzylidene)-amines with 2-mercapto-4,4,6-trimethyl-1H,4H,1,3-thiazine.

Some pyrimidobenzothiazines¹⁻³, synthesised earlier, having shown antibacterial activity, it was considered desirable to introduce amino group in position 6 and to study their antibacterial and antimalarial activity. These have been synthesised by the condensation of various (2-amino-4,5-methylenedioxybenzylidene) amines (I) with β -isothioyanoketones (II), the probable mechanism being:

Fig. 1

1. Gill et al., *J. Org. Chem.*, 1961, 26, 988.
 2. Sharma, *ibid.*, 1963, 28, 740.

The above mechanism visualises the formation of two possible products (IV) and (V) through the intermediate (III). In the present case, however, only one product is formed. These compounds could be assigned the pyrimidobenzothiazine structure (V) on the basis of previous experience^{1,2} and by comparing some of them with the isomeric thiazinoquinazolines (IV), prepared by unambiguous synthesis. The data regarding their yields, solvents of crystallisation and analytical results is shown in Table I.

It is quite interesting that these pyrimidobenzothiazines on treatment with ethanolic HCl undergo retrogression to give rise to benzothiazine derivatives and mesityl oxide. The retrogression could be represented as:

Thiazinoquinazolines: Besides evaluating antibacterial and antimalarial activity in this series, the interest in the synthesis of thiazinoquinazolines was to compare them with isomeric product (V) obtained above. These have been obtained by the condensation of (2-amino-4,5-methylenedioxybenzylidene) amines with 2-mercapto-4, 4, 6-trimethyl-1*H*, 4*H*, 1,3-thiazines. The reaction could be visualised to take place as follows:

The thiazinoquinazolines (Table II), thus obtained by unambiguous route, were found to be different from their isomeric products (Table I first three) obtained above.

These thiazino-quinazolines also on treatment with EtOH-HCl solution of hydrochloric acid undergo retrogression to give rise to 2-mercapto-4-amino tetrahydro quinazoline and mesityl oxide.

The data regarding these thiazinoquinazolines are recorded in Table II.

* EXPERIMENTAL

Synthesis of 1,3,3-Trimethyl-6-anilino-3H, 6H-pyrimido-(1,2a) (3,1)-benso-thiazines:—(2-Amino-4,5-methylene-dioxybenzylidene), aniline (2.40 g) and 2-methyl 2-isothiocyanopenta-4-one (1.67 g) were mixed together and heated on a steam bath. First the contents became mobile, but as the reaction proceeded, the mass began to solidify. After 4-5 hours' heating, the product was cooled and crystallised from ethanol, the yield being 2.33 g. Other Schiff bases were also condensed with β -isothiocyanoketones under similar conditions.

Synthesis of 2,4,4-Trimethyl-6-anilino-4H, 6H (1,3)-thiazino-(2,3b)-quinazoline:—A mixture of (2-amino-4,5-methylenedioxy-benzylidene) aniline (0.01M, 2.40 g.) and 2-mercapto-4,4,6-trimethyl-1H, 4H, 1,3-thiazine (0.10M, 1.71 g) was heated in an oil bath at 110-20° when the contents became mobile with the evolution of H_2S . After heating for 2½ hr. the temperature was raised to 140-50° for ¼ hr for the completion of the reaction. At this stage, the evolution of H_2S practically ceased. After cooling, the sticky product was crystallised from ethanol, the yield being 1.17 g. Other Schiff bases were also condensed with 2-mercapto-4,4,6-trimethyl-1H, 4H, 1,3-thiazine under similar conditions.

*Analysis are by Mr. B. N. Anand of the Punjab University Chemistry Department, Chandigarh-3.

TABLE I

R=	Yield	*M.P.	Formula	Found	Reqd.
A. Ketone used—2-methyl-2-isothiocyanopenta-4-one.					
Ph	59%	191°	C ₁₁ H ₂₁ O ₂ N ₂ S	N : 11.15%	11.08%
-C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃ (p)	63	194°	C ₁₂ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₂ S	N : 10.60	10.27
-C ₆ H ₄ OC ₂ H ₅ (p)	64	200°	C ₁₃ H ₂₃ O ₂ N ₂ S	C : 65.01 H : 6.20	65.25 5.91
-C ₆ H ₄ Cl(p)	64	205°	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₂ ClS	N : 10.20 N : 10.60	9.93 10.13
B. Ketone used—3-methyl-3-isothiocyanoohepta-5-one R—Me; R'—R''—Et					
Ph	39	206°	C ₁₃ H ₂₃ O ₂ N ₂ S	N : 10.21	10.32
-C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃ (p)	42	209°	C ₁₄ H ₂₇ O ₂ N ₂ S	N : 9.93	9.61
-C ₆ H ₄ OC ₂ H ₅ (p)	43	216°	C ₁₅ H ₂₉ O ₂ N ₂ S	N : 9.45	9.31
C. Ketone used—2-methyl-2-isothiocyanohexa-4-one. R'=R''=Me; R'''=Et					
Ph	46	194°	C ₁₂ H ₂₃ O ₂ N ₂ S	N : 10.50	10.69
-C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃ (p)	48	197°	C ₁₃ H ₂₇ O ₂ N ₂ S	N : 10.22	9.93
-C ₆ H ₄ OC ₂ H ₅ (p)	50	198°	C ₁₄ H ₂₇ O ₂ N ₂ S	N : 9.76	9.61
-C ₆ H ₄ Cl(p)	40	197°	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂ ClS	N : 10.12	9.80

*Crystallised from EtOH

TABLE II

R.	Yield	*M.P.	Formula	Analytical results Found	Reqd.
-C ₆ H ₅	81%	200°	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₃ S	N : 10.79%	11.08%
-C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃ (p)	36	182°	C ₂₂ H ₂₃ N ₃ O ₃ S	N : 10.02 C : 64.25 H : 6.00	10.27 64.55 5.62
-C ₆ H ₄ OC ₂ H ₅	38	208°	C ₂₃ H ₂₅ N ₃ O ₃ S	N : 9.65	9.93

*Crystallised from EtOH

Treatment of 1,3,3-Trimethyl-6-(p-methoxyanilino)-3H, 6H-pyrimido- (1,2a) (3,1)-benzothiazine with EtOH-HCl:—1, 3, 3-Trimethyl 6-(p-methoxyanilino)-3H, 6H-pyrimido- (1,2a) (3,1)-benzothiazine (5 g.) was dissolved in a saturated solution of EtOH—HCl (50 ml) and then refluxed on a steam bath for 10 hr. and finally subjected to vacuum distillation. The distillate obtained was treated with 2,4 dinitrophenylhydrazine and the hydrazone formed was crystallised from dilute ethanol. It was confirmed to be 2,4 DNP hydrazone of mesityl oxide, as established by its m.p. and mixed m.p. with an authentic sample. The residue after basification with sodium carbonate and washing with water was crystallised from ethanol in brown plates, m.p. 208°, yield 1.1 g. (Found: N, 12, 21. C₁₆H₁₇N₃O₃S requires N, 12.76%).

Treatment of 2,4,4-Trimethyl-6 (p-methoxyanilino)-4H,6H-(1,3) thiazino (2,3b)-quinazoline with alcoholic hydrochloric acid:—2,4,4-Trimethyl-6 (p-methoxyanilino)

4H, 6H- (1,3)-thiazino (2,3b) quinoxaline (5 g.) was dissolved in ethanol. After cooling it was saturated with HCl gas and refluxed on a steam bath for 9 hr. Finally it was subjected to vacuum distillation. From the distillate 2,4-D.N.P was prepared and crystallised as above. It was confirmed to be 2,4 DNP of mesity oxide by its m. p. and undepressed mixed m.p. with an authentic sample. The residue was neutralised with sodium carbonate solution and after washing with water crystallised from ethanol in brownish plates, m.p. 163°, yield 2.2 g. (Found: N, 12.36. $C_{10}H_{10}N_2O_2S$ requires N, 12.76%).

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